

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Hertwig**FIRST NAME:** Friederike**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **In academic writing, plagiarism is not acceptable and needs to be avoided. Which are the two forms of plagiarism?**

- Not using quotation marks when using the words of a source, and paraphrasing in your own words, but keeping the information's message the same.
- Paraphrasing too close to the source and editing the quotation in italics.
- Not using quotation marks when using the words of a source, and taking the idea of a source, but not adding the citation or footnote.¹**
- Adding a citation to a quotation and paraphrasing in your own words but keeping the information's message the same.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 16.

2. **Italics are used for keywords, titles, words referred to as words or foreign terms. How often do you use italics for the same term in a paper?**

- Only the first time it is used in a paper.²**
- Every time the term comes up during the paper.
- Only in the first paragraph, the term comes up.
- Only in reference lists.

3. **How should researchers reconsider their research question?**

- When the question is too difficult to be answered, you have too many references available, and you cannot plausibly disprove the answer.
- When the main references are not available in the English language, when you can answer the question too easily, and the question has been asked before.
- When you can answer the question too easily, you find too much evidence to support the answer, and you cannot plausibly disprove the answer.
- When you can answer the question too easily, you cannot find good evidence to support the answer, and you cannot plausibly disprove the answer.³**

4. **What information should the introduction of your report include?**

² Ibid., 47.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb and Joseph M. Williams, (Chicago: University of Chicago Press., 2013), 20.

- State the main findings, show the reader what evidence you found to answer your research question, and introduce the reader to the subject.
 - Summarize the content of your report, show the reader what evidence you found to answer your research question, and give them a framework for understanding.
 - Put your research in the context of other research, make readers understand why they should read your report, and give them a framework for understanding it.**⁴
 - Put your research in the context of other research, summarize the main findings that you found, and introduce the reader to the subject.
5. **In Notes-Bibliography Style citing, how do you cite the footnote of a book when using the reference for the first time?**
- Author's First and Last Names, Year of Publication, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name), page numbers.
 - Author's Last Name, Year of Publication, the page number of references used.
 - Author's Last Name, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of publication), page numbers.
 - Author's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of publication), page numbers.**⁵
6. **Name three types of bibliographies in Notes-Bibliography Style citation mentioned in *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*.**

⁴ Ibid., 70.

⁵ Ibid., 91.

- Selected bibliography, single-author bibliography, and annotated bibliography.**⁶
 - Analytical bibliography, single-author bibliography, ad annotated bibliography.
 - Selected bibliography, single year bibliography, and annotated bibliography.
 - Enumerative bibliography, single year bibliography, and annotated bibliography.
7. **In chapter three, the methodology chapter, the research design has different approaches. Some can be combined. Name three main qualitative research approaches.**
- Phenomenological approach, Narrative, and Ontology.
 - Case Study, Epistemology, and Ground theory.
 - Narrative, Ethnography, and Ground theory.**⁷
 - Ethnography, Ontology, and Axiology.
8. **The conceptual framework plays a central role in your dissertation. It is presented at the end of chapter two, the literature review. What are the two steps to develop a conceptual framework?**
- Developing categories and find examples for each category from the sources used in the literature review.

⁶ Ibid., 93

⁷ Philip Adu, "Conducting Qualitative Research - Writing the Methodology Chapter," March 6, 2013, accessed November 22, 2020, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&feature=emb_logo

- Developing categories and develop descriptors for each category.**⁸
 - Summarize research approaches from all sources and develop categories.
 - List concepts that sources used and develop descriptors for each category.
9. **While presenting your findings in chapter four should be as objective as possible, what guidelines should you follow in chapter five when interpreting your findings?**
- Subjective, current, logical, and credible.
 - Clear, logical, short, and credible.
 - Clear, logical, relevant, and credible.**⁹
 - Logical, objective, relevant, and credible.
10. **In the international dating system, how is a date used?**
- Month (spelled out) day (numbers XX), year (numbers XXXX).
 - Day (numbers XX) Month (spelled out) year (numbers XXXX).
 - Year-month-date (all numbers XXXX-XX-XX).**¹⁰
 - Month-date-year (all numbers XX-XX-XXXX).

⁸ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 56 – 57.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 136-137.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 25.

REFERENCES

- Adu, Philip. "Conducting Qualitative Research - Writing the Methodology Chapter". YouTube video, March 6, 2013. Accessed November 22, 2020, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&feature=emb_logo.
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- Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
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Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.